

Counsellor-Trainees' Perceptions On The Necessity Of Electronic Communication In Counselling Practices

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ABSTRACT

The advent of technology has revolutionized the field of counseling, enabling therapists to reach a wider client base and provide more accessible services. Electronic communication, in particular, has become an essential tool in counseling practices. The study examines the necessity for the utilization of electronic communication in counseling practices among counselor-trainees in Ekiti State University with the view to exploring the benefits, limitations and ethical considerations in using electronic communication in counselling. The descriptive survey design was used in the study. The simple random sampling technique was used in selecting Two hundred counsellor- trainees of the Ekiti State University Regular Degree program in Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo. The main instrument used for data collection was 'Necessity of ICT in Counsellors "Professional Practice Scale'. One research question and two null hypotheses were proposed for the study. Simple percentage and t-test statistical methods were used in analyzing the data collected respectively. The findings show that majority of Counsellor-trainees have positive perceptions towards the necessity of e-communication in counseling and that no significant differences existed in the perceptions of counsellor-trainees based on gender and educational level. It was recommended that guidance counsellors should of necessity train in the use of electronic communication to make counselling practice more effective and that the University management should ensure appropriate facilities in place for the training of highly effective counsellors who can compete with their foreign counterparts.

Keywords: Perceptions, Counselling Practices, Electronic Communication, Counselling-trainees

INTRODUCTION

Communication as a concept originates from the Latin word 'communicare' which literally means 'to put in common' or 'to share.' It consists of transmitting information from one person to another (Idowu & Esere, 2007). In another way, communication is described as the production and exchange of information and meaning by use of signs and symbols. According to the authors, communication permeates all levels of human experience and it is central to understanding human behaviour and to nearly all helping relationship efforts aimed at fostering behaviour change among individuals and societies. Communication is a pillar which maintains the structure of peaceful co-existence and mutual understanding; it is very vital in all areas of human life including counselling and is used to persuade, to influence relationships, to inform, share, discover and uncover information.

Counseling, also known as psychotherapy, is a process that involves a trained therapist working with an individual, group, or family to help them cope with mental health issues, relationship problems, or other challenges (Corey, 2017). Traditional counseling practices involve face-to-face interactions between the

therapist and client. However, with the rapid advancement of technology, electronic communication has become increasingly popular in counseling practices (Maheu, 2012). According to Action Health Incorporated (2002), "counseling is a client-oriented interactive communication process in which one helps others make free informed decisions about their personal behaviour and provide support to sustain that behaviour" The importance of communication in counselling cannot be over emphasized because information is the foundation on which the counsellor builds his services.

Counseling has been on in Africa for some time. Counseling services have been done mostly in 'face to face' form where the counsellor and clients are in physical contact during counselling sessions because it is believed that eye contact makes counselling more effective. In the past few decades however, Information Technology Communication (ICT) tools have drastically changed the global economy and the way people communicate (Olaleye, 2010). Counseling psychologists are not left out in this all-important development. ICT has significantly transformed various spheres of human life: agriculture, medicine, engineering etc. It also has potential to transform counselling practices and it must be noted as emphasized by Lindon and Lindon (2000) that computers should not take over from personal contact by telephone or face to face. According to these scholars, electronic communication is an addition and not a replacement.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) which is one of the new trends in education has become very popular in educational settings (OraegbLinam, 2009). For effective educational service delivery, Maduaburn (2004) and Okebukola (1997) reiterated that information and communication technology among other things must be made available to teachers, counsellors and students. This point necessitates the need for a paradigm shift in delivering counselling services in the Nigerian society.

Electronic communication involves the use of e-mails, internet and other computer aided strategies in counselling clients. Yusop, Sulaiman and Abdullah (2010) opined that the emergence of the internet has transformed the society to an information society, while Moursund (1995) stated that technology literacy is among the three basic skills for citizens of an information age, besides information literacy and visual literacy skills. In the counselling profession, technology literacy is an essential skill a counsellor must master. Some forms of electronic counselling include: e-mail counseling. Therapists and clients communicate via email, exchanging messages and attachments (Fenichel, 2002). Also, therapists and clients engage in real-time video sessions using platforms like Zoom, Skype, or Google Meet (Maheu, 2012). Again, therapists and clients communicate via instant messaging apps, such as WhatsApp or Facebook Messenger (Hilty, 2013). Lastly, therapists can make good use of specialized platforms, like BetterHelp or Talkspace, connect therapists with clients and provide a secure online environment for counseling (Barnett, 2015).

A number of arguments have been made in favour of electronic service provision. These include the ability of email and internet contact to facilitate access to services, client privacy and disclosure, and ongoing client support and facilitating face to face (FF) contact (Ainsworth, 2002); Bradley, Sullivan, & King, 2003; Caleb, 2000; Hamilton, 1999; Health Service Division, 2003; Hsiung, 2002; Koppel, 2001; Sampson, Kolodinsky, & Greeno, 1997). Electronic communication in counselling has a number of benefits. It leads to increased accessibility. It enables therapists to reach clients who may be geographically isolated, have mobility issues, or prefer the convenience of online counseling (Kessler, 2005). Also, it offers flexibility to the process of counselling. It allows therapists to offer flexible scheduling options, including evening and weekend sessions (Rochlen, 2004). Electronic counselling could also be cost effective. According to Kazdin (2003), online counseling can reduce costs associated with traditional face-to-face counseling, such as transportation and office overhead. Again, electronic counselling provides a sense of anonymity, which may encourage clients to disclose sensitive information (Suler, 2004).

However, some practitioners have also argued against the practice especially as it affects the privacy of clients. Some of the limitations of electronic counselling have been identified. First of this is technical issues. Connectivity problems, poor video quality, or software glitches can disrupt counselling sessions (Kazdin, 2003). Also, there is the problem of limited non-verbal cues: Electronic communication can

make it difficult to read nonverbal cues, such as body language or tone of voice (Suler, 2004). Again, there is security and confidentiality concerns. Electronic communication requires robust security measures to protect client confidentiality and ensure HIPAA compliance (Barnett, 2015). Lastly, lack of necessary skills could hamper practice. Therapists must develop the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively use electronic communication in counseling (Maheu, 2012).

Some ethical considerations must be made however, if electronic counselling will be effective. First and foremost, clients must provide informed consent before engaging in electronic communication counseling (American Counseling Association, 2014). Also, therapists must ensure the confidentiality and security of client's information transmitted electronically (National Board for Certified Counselors, 2016). Again, therapists must be sensitive to cultural and linguistic differences when communicating electronically (American Psychological Association, 2017) and lastly, therapists must establish clear boundaries and guidelines for electronic communication (Corey, 2017). If all these are adhered to, electronic counselling will be highly effective and preferred.

Statement of the Problem

The use of electronic mail (email) and the Internet are no longer novelties but fixtures in numerous workplaces and the leisure activities of many. Since the mid-1990s counsellors and psychologists have debated the use of email and the Internet in applied work. However in Nigeria, counsellors are still battling with arguments on availability, accessibility and usage of Information Communication Technologies (ICT) for counselling purposes. It is on this premise that the researcher was motivated to conduct this study.

Research Questions

The study is guided by the following research questions:

- i. What is the general perception of Counsellor-trainees on the benefits of electronic counselling in counselling practices in the Nigerian society?

Research Hypotheses

- i. There is no significant difference in the perceptions of counsellor-trainees on the necessity of electronic communication in counselling based on gender.
- ii. There is no significant difference in the perceptions of counsellor-trainees on the necessity of electronic communication in counselling based on educational levels.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research is descriptive in nature, thus the researcher employed the descriptive research design in carrying out the study.

Population and Sample

The population of the study included five hundred (500) Ekiti State University Regular Degree program. However, because of limited time and resources, the researcher used the simple random sampling technique to select two hundred counsellor-trainees from 300 and 400 levels; these are assumed to be more experienced and exposed than other levels of trainees.

Instrumentation

The main instrument used in data collection was a self-designed scale titled "Necessity of ICT in Counsellors' Professional Practice Scale". The scale has two sections (A & B). Section A contains demographic details of respondents, while section B contains fifteen question items, which border on the need for the use of ICT in counselling practices of counsellor-trainees.

The instrument was subjected to screening by experts in psychometrics and counselling psychology. The experts' various suggestions were included in the final draft of the scale; this ensured its face and content validity. To establish the reliability of the scale, the researcher conducted a test-retest reliability which yielded 0.95 alpha value.

Procedure for Data Collection

The researcher personally administered the instrument on the study participants. Having explained the purpose of the study, the researcher distributed the questionnaires and allowed participants about 30 minutes to respond to the scale. After this, the researcher went round to retrieve the questionnaires.

Data Analysis

Simple percentage method was used in analyzing data for the research question, while t-test statistical method was used in analyzing the two null hypotheses.

RESULTS

The results of the data collected are hereby presented according to the research questions raised in the study.

Research Question 1: *What is the general perception of Counsellor-trainees on the benefits of electronic counselling in counselling practices in the Nigerian society?*

Table 1: Showing the general perceptions of counsellor-trainees on the

Question	Agree	%	Disagree	%	Decision	Rank
E-counselling regulates the counselor’s emotion	165	84.5	31	15.5	Positive	7 th
E-counselling could be more economical	136	68.0	64	32.0	Positive	10 th
E-counselling consumes lesser time	181	90.5	19	9.5	Positive	3 rd
E-counselling could be more confidential	155	77.5	45	22.5	Positive	8 th
E-counselling makes the counselor ICT compliant	176	88	24	12	Positive	4 th
E-counselling has no geographical limitation/gap	173	86.5	27	13.5	Positive	5 th
E-counselling enhances client-driven frequency	144	72.0	56	28.0	Positive	9 th
E-counselling provides accessibility to individuals who are disabled and housebound	195	97.5	05	2.5	Positive	1 st
E-counselling makes the client more relaxed and tension-free	172	86	28	14	Positive	6 th

The table above shows that all the question items were positively responded to by counsellor-trainees. It implies that counsellor-trainees perceived e-counselling to be highly necessary for counselling practice. The responses were ranked in order of importance of the benefits listed.

Hypotheses

The results of the tested hypotheses are hereby presented in tables.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in the perceptions of counselor trainees on the necessity of electronic communication in counselling based on gender.

Table I: Showing the differences in the perceptions of counsellor-trainees based on gender

Variables	N	X	SD	df	t-obs	t-crit	P
Male	86	36.62	71.72	198	0.54	1.96	Accepted
Female	114	19.80	59.41				

The result in table I above reveals the perceptions of counsellor-trainees based on gender. The male (86) has a mean of 36.62 with the Standard Deviation of 71.72, while female (114) has a mean of 19.80 and Standard Deviation of 59.41. The t-obs is 0.54, while the t-crit is 1.96. Since the value of t-obs. (0.54) is

lesser than the t-crit., the null hypothesis is hereby accepted, meaning that no significant difference exists in the perceptions of male and female counsellor-trainees on the necessity of electronic counselling.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in the perceptions of counsellor-trainees on the necessity of electronic communication in counselling based on educational level.

Table II: Showing the differences in the perceptions of counsellor-trainees based on educational level.

Variables	N	X	SD	df	t-obs	t-crit	P
300 level	100	48.59	6.08	198	1.10	1.96	Accepted
400level	100	49.53	5.97				

The result in table II above reveals the differences in the perceptions of counsellor-trainees based on educational levels. The counsellor-trainee in 300L (100) has a mean (x) of 48.59, with Standard Deviation of 6.08, while 400L has a mean (x) of 49.53 and a Standard Deviation of 5.97. The t.obs value is 1.10, while that of t.irit is 1.96. The null hypothesis is hereby accepted because the t.obs (1.10) is lesser than the t.crit. (1.96). collectively, more than 500 more e-therapists

DISCUSSION

Research question one above sought to know counsellor-trainees' general perceptions of Counsellor-trainees on the benefits of electronic counseling in counselling practices in the Nigerian society. The respondents were to answer questions on their perceptions of benefits of e-counselling. Ten major benefits were listed and the responses on all the factors were positive, meaning all the listed benefit are significant to counselling practices.

The benefits were later ranked according to the responses of participants. The benefit that e-Counselling provides accessibility to individuals who are disabled and housebound, ranked 1" while the second says that e-Counselling is more flexible. The third benefit states that e-Counselling consumes lesser time, while the forth states that ICT use will make counsellor-trainees ICT compliant. All the responses are not out of place as they confirm earlier studies (e.g Anyamene, Nwokolo, & Anyachebelu, 2010; Smith & Collins, 2004) who all affirmed that the benefits of ICT in counselling practices could be enormous.

Hypothesis one aimed at finding the difference in the perceptions of counsellor-trainees on the necessity of electronic communication in counselling based on gender. The finding revealed that no significant difference exists in the perceptions of male and female counsellor-trainees on the necessity of electronic counselling. It means that both male and female counselor-trainees agree to the fact that ICT is very paramount to the practice of counselling. This result is not in isolation as it corroborates the findings of Offer and Watts (2000) who found that school counselors (male and female) are increasingly recognizing the benefits of using computer technology to increase their efficiency, to assist in the supervision of counseling interns, to aid in delivering developmental guidance lessons, and to facilitate individual counseling areas such as bibliotherapy. The finding is also a confirmation of Ainsworth (2000) who found that there were over 300 private practice websites where e-therapists offered services and e-clinics which represented, collectively, more than 500 more e-therapists (male and female inclusive).

This result is expected because all professions are becoming ICT driven, and any profession that is not ICT compliant is looked down with disdain and infact witnesses low output in its productivity. This possibly informs the decision of the counselor-trainees in perceiving ICT as being vital in counselling practices. Also, in an exploratory study of clients' perceptions of online counselling, Liebert, Archer, Munson, & York (2006) found that clients (male and female) agreed that online counselling is highly beneficial.

Hypothesis two sought to find the difference in the perceptions of counsellor-trainees on the necessity of electronic communication in counselling based on educational level. This result shows that counsellor-trainees at both levels selected for the study agreed that ICT utilization is vital to the operations of counselling. This is possibly the participants do not want to be cut off by the wind of change blowing over all professions in the world of work. Studies within and outside Nigeria (e.g N dum & Onukwuga,

2013; Offer, & Watts, 2000; and Mallen, & Vogel, 2005) all found that counsellors all over the world are embracing the use of ICT in counselling practices. These levels of counsellor-trainees were selected because they are more experienced than other levels of trainees.

(Olademi & Oladipo, (2006), Bolaji, (2007) and Kelly, (2004) while describing Nigeria's position in global technology arena noted that there was a gap between average Nigerian student's knowledge in computer skills and the computer skill of other students from other countries around the world. This in the researcher's opinion informed the counsellor-trainees' perceptions in wanting to embrace ICT in counselling practice.

CONCLUSION

Electronic communication has transformed the field of counseling, offering numerous benefits, including increased accessibility, flexibility, and cost-effectiveness. However, therapists must be aware of the limitations and challenges associated with electronic communication, including technical issues, limited nonverbal cues, and security concerns. By addressing these challenges and adhering to ethical guidelines, therapists can effectively integrate electronic communication into their counseling practices, ultimately enhancing the therapeutic experience for clients.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In line with the above findings, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Government at all levels should encourage counseling practices by fully equipping the counselling clinics with modern electronic gadgets to make counseling more effective for practitioners.
- ii. Counselors should enroll for ICT training so as to be ICT compliant.
- iii. The curriculum of counselor-trainees should be adequately revisited to accommodate the training in ICT by would be counselors.

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